

Ternary Complexes of Neodymium Ion with Picolinic, Thiodiglycolic and Thiodipropionic as Primary Ligands and Some Dicarboxylic Acids as Secondary Ligands

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pH titration method has been used to calculate the simple and mixed-ligand stabilities of neodymium complexes with carboxylic acids at 30° and $\mu = 0.1M$ (NaClO₄). Picolinic, thiodiglycolic and thiodipropionic acids were used as primary and malonic, succinic, itaconic, glutaric and adipic as secondary ligands respectively. Neodymium ion forms 1:1 and 1:2 complexes with only picolinic acid. The equilibrium constants such as K_{DXY} , K_{aXY} , K_{aYX} and $\Delta \log K$ were utilized to explain the preferential formation of ternary complexes over binary ones.

THE simple and mixed-ligand systems of lanthanides with carboxylic acid have been investigated¹⁻³. Ramamoorthy and Manning⁴ studied exhaustively, the mixed-ligand chelates of meso-dl-tartaric acid with divalent and trivalent metals, particularly neodymium ion. Recently, Darnall and Birnbaum^{5,6} showed that a lanthanide ion could substitute for calcium ion and produce an active enzyme system. In that study it was shown that neodymium was a better stimulator for the conversion of trypsinogen to trypsin than the calcium ion. Considering the biological significance of neodymium ion⁷, the present work is aimed to investigate the mixed-ligand systems of this metal ion with pyridine carboxylic, thiodicarboxylic and aliphatic dicarboxylic acids and to examine the complexing ability of these dicarboxylic acids 1:1 Nd³⁺-picolinic acid complex.

Experimental

Picolinic, thiodiglycolic and thiodipropionic acids were obtained from Fluka (Germany) while malonic, succinic, adipic, itaconic, glutaric were of B.D.H. (AnalaR) grade. The purity of these acids was checked by their melting points. Neodymium perchlorate was prepared by the standard procedure. The concentration of Nd(III) in original solution was estimated as Nd₂O₃. All solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The details of the pH measurements and other chemicals are given in an earlier paper⁸.

Results and Discussion

The acid dissociation constants of the acids and stability constants of the simple complexes were evaluated by the method of Irving and Rossotti⁹ (Table 1). The formation of the mixed-ligand

chelate was confirmed to be in a simultaneous equilibrium according to the procedure of Carey and Martell¹⁰. The mixed-ligand stabilities and other equilibrium constants were calculated by the procedure⁴ and are presented in Table 2. The possible complexation equilibria of the simple and mixed-ligand systems of the metal ions are outlined in our earlier communications^{11,12}.

In the series under investigation picolinic acid can be considered as a primary ligand and malonic, succinic, itaconic, glutaric, thiodiglycolic, adipic and thiodipropionic which can respectively form six, seven, seven, eight, eight, nine and ten membered rings as secondary ligands. Picolinic acid forms 1:1 and 1:2 chelates while all the remaining acids form only 1:1 complexes with neodymium ion in the pH range 2.5-5.0. The coordination of Nd³⁺ with picolinic acid takes place through the oxygen of -COO⁻ group and nitrogen of the pyridine ring. The five-membered chelate ring of picolinic acid with vanadyl have been reported¹³.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF NEODYMIUM COMPLEXES WITH CARBOXYLIC ACIDS

Temp. 30 ± 0.1°	$\mu = 0.1M$ (NaClO ₄)
Ligand/acids	Stability constant (log K)
Picolinic	3.96 (3.04)*
Thiodiglycolic	3.22
Thiodipropionic	3.21
Malonic	4.21
Succinic	3.38
Itaconic	3.77
Glutaric	3.01
Adipic	2.90

* log K_a value,
pK values are taken from reference 1 and 11.

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TABLE 2—LOGARITHMS OF EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS FOR TERNARY CHELATES OF Nd^{3+} -PICOLINIC/THIODIACIDS ($\text{HY}/\text{H}_2\text{Y}$)-SECONDARY (H_2X) LIGAND ACIDS

Acid/systems	$\mu = 0.1M (\text{NaClO}_4)$				
	Temp. $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$	β_{XY}	K_{DXY}	$K_{2\text{XY}}$	$K_{2\text{YX}}$
Picolinic*-malonic	7.31	0.06	3.10	3.35	-0.86
Picolinic-succinic	7.89	1.47	4.51	3.93	+0.55
Picolinic-itaconic	7.26	0.46	3.49	3.30	-0.46
Picolinic-glutaric	7.49	1.44	4.48	3.53	+0.52
Picolinic-adipic	6.69	0.72	3.79	2.73	-0.17
Picolinic-thiodiglycolic	6.33	0.07	3.11	2.73	-0.85
Picolinic-thiodipropionic	7.19	0.94	3.98	3.23	+0.02
Thiodiglycolic**malonic	6.07	-1.36	1.86	2.85	-1.36
Thiodiglycolic-succinic	5.14	-1.46	1.76	1.92	-1.46
Thiodiglycolic-itaconic	5.59	-1.40	1.82	2.37	-1.40
Thiodiglycolic-glutaric	5.07	-1.16	0.06	1.85	-1.16
Thiodiglycolic-adipic	4.67	-1.45	1.87	1.45	-1.45
Thiodipropionic**malonic	7.52	0.10	3.31	4.31	+0.10
Thiodipropionic-succinic	7.52	0.93	4.14	4.31	+0.93
Thiodipropionic-itaconic	7.51	0.53	3.74	4.30	+0.53
Thiodipropionic-glutaric	7.23	1.01	4.22	4.02	+1.01
Thiodipropionic-adipic	8.56	2.45	5.66	5.35	+2.45

* $K_{\text{DXY}} = K(\text{MX} + \text{MY} \rightleftharpoons \text{MXY} + \text{MY})$,

** $K_{\text{DXY}} = K(\text{MX} + \text{MY} \rightleftharpoons \text{MXY} + \text{M})$.

The accuracy of β_{XY} values was between 0.01 and 0.10 log units.

Nd^{3+} -picolinic-secondary Ligand Acids :

$\Delta \log K$ values (Table 2) are negative except for the Nd^{3+} -picolinic-succinic, Nd^{3+} -picolinic-glutaric and Nd^{3+} -picolinic-thiodipropionic acid systems. $\Delta \log K$ value for Nd^{3+} -picolinic-thiodipropionic is +0.02 which is close to zero, indicating that ternary complex is formed to the same extent as the binary ones. The K_{DXY} values are close to predicted on statistical consideration for these systems, however, these are significantly small in Nd^{3+} -picolinic-malonic and Nd^{3+} -picolinic-thiodipropionic acid systems.

A comparison of $K_{2\text{XY}}$ and K_{MY_2} and $K_{2\text{YX}}$ and K_{MX_2} , reveals the preferential formation of ternary complexes over binary except for the systems involving secondary ligands, succinic, glutaric and thiodipropionic acids. The $K_{2\text{YX}}$ and β_{XY} values follow the order : succinic > glutaric > malonic > itaconic > thiodipropionic > adipic > thiodiglycolic.

Nd^{3+} -thiodicarboxylic-secondary Ligand Acids :

The $\Delta \log K$ values are negative for Nd^{3+} -thiodiglycolic-secondary while positive for Nd^{3+} -thiodipropionic-secondary ligands. Nd^{3+} -thiodipropionic-secondary ligand systems have positive values for disproportionation reaction. The ternary chelate in this series, are thus mostly formed by the reaction $\text{MX} + \text{MY} \rightleftharpoons \text{MXY} + \text{M}$.¹⁴

The order of $K_{2\text{YX}}$ and ΣpK are :

- (i) malonic > itaconic > succinic > glutaric > adipic
 (ii) adipic < glutaric < succinic < itaconic < malonic.

The values of $K_{2\text{XY}}$ and K_{MY_2} for thiodiglycolic-secondary ligand indicate the preferential formation of the ternary complex by the reaction $\text{MX} + \text{Y} \rightleftharpoons \text{MXY}$. The formation of ternary complex is mainly dependent on ring size of the chelate which seems to offset the increasing basicity of the secondary ligands observed from the increase relationship between $K_{2\text{YX}}$ and the product of the acid dissociation constants.

The order of β_{XY} with reference to secondary ligands is the same as $K_{2\text{YX}}$ and are in accordance to the 1:1 binary stabilities. The plots of β_{XY} against K_{MX_2} , gave direct linear relationship.

However, for thiodipropionic-secondary ligands the plots of $K_{2\text{YX}}$ against ΣpK and β_{XY} against K_{MX_2} , do not give any linear relationship. This is due to the strain involved in ten-membered ring, which do not prefer to add the secondary ligand to form the mixed-ligand complex.

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